

MEDIA LITERACY. FAKE NEWS IN SOCIAL MEDIA

Kadirova Umida

Journalism and Mass
Communication University of Uzbekistan

Fake news is really a symptom of
much larger problems,
including the lack of media literacy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8058173>

Nowadays news spread fast we couldn't image how will be result of this occasion. Surely, this kind of mechanism use bad minded persons for destroying public mind or in severe condition can be cause of crime. So, it is important that people should be informed about media literacy. Nowadays social media is platform for spreading fake news and propaganda. The social media phenomenon began in the new millennium around 2003 .

One of the first social media network to attract a great number of users was Myspace. Myspace is a social media network that enables users to create a personalized wall, and have their friends visit their digital wall of likes and dislikes. This was also the place to post pictures, songs, videos and was digital way of being unique. Currently, Facebook, Twitter, and Google+ are a few of the more popular social media websites today. The more popular social media websites are centered around a wall of information that is populated by friends and advertisers. Social media has helped increase communication and information travel internationally and across borders. Nowadays there are 4.9 billion people use social media worldwide. (Statistics of June 2023) It is forecasted that this number will reach 5.85 billion by the year 2027. Social media is used by 85% of the world's 5.27 billion mobile phone users. An average person uses social media for two hours and thirty-five minutes every day around the globe.

The uses of social media are varied, but they do have a common goal. All have main purpose to share thoughts, information, picture or video. Each user of social media can put every material that want. But others don't know is it true or fake. Un-truthful information can be spread purposely or accidental. Un-truthful information that is spread purposely can be done as a satire or to instigate an emotional response. Un-truthful information is also spread un-purposely by the thousands of users of social media. All kinds of fake information and new used provocative headlines. In recent years, however, fake news has been responsible for a great deal of misinformation because more and more people have begun consuming and believing these articles without bothering to fact check or even read beyond the headlines. This acceptance of incorrect information has led to confusion, panic, and an inability to discuss the actual facts surrounding current events

Recent studies have shown that an estimated 59 percent of social media users will share information without actually reading an article, but will share information based on the title alone.

Social media has a great power to affect a social change on society. Social media has allowed thousands of people, if not millions, to have a voice and spread the information that the user feels is relevant and important. Unfortunately, with one fake news all society can destroy. Also, has effectively changed the way that the new generation of society gains access to newsworthy information from reliable and un-reliable sources. Advantage or disadvantage of social media is access to information available 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, 365 days a year. So, how to check it firstly it can be difficult, but all of us should read critically all information on social media. For checking it there some ideas that easily can be found fakes.

- Firstly, Enter the keywords of the story into a search engine and get some opinion from a credible news site with verifiable sources.
- Check the dates involved in the article. Writers of fake news sometimes take a real story from the past, put an outrageous headline on it, and try to pass it off as a current event.
- Find the source of the author's information for the article. If there is not any source it can't be truthful information. Also, URL should be legitimate.
- The website's appearance is also important. Some fake news sites mimic the appearance of legitimate news sources, tricking the casual reader. Truthful website has address, phone number or gmail for contacting.
- Take a look at the headlines of other stories from the same website. Many authors write provocative headline to attract audience. So, many of them will unbelievable, shocking, stimulative, inflammatory.
- Some of news there are some jokes. Because author want to hide main information beside of humorous stories based on current events.

People don't be hurry up to take information of any social media platform. Unfortunately, they do it unthinking the result. Thus, all users of social media should be alert. "We hear a lot about "fake news," but that term, which was coined fairly recently, is really a symptom of much larger problems, including the lack of media literacy. In fact, Stanford Graduate School of Education recently found that more than 80% of middle and high school students surveyed were unable to distinguish between advertisements and real news stories. As parents and educators, it's our job to help our students become more savvy consumers of information. But it's not just kids who need a lesson in media literacy. Adults do as well. A 2016 Pew study

found that nearly a quarter of adults admit to sharing fake news in the past. Most didn't know it was fake when they shared it".

So important moment there is huge difference between fact and opinion.

Fact- High-quality news should focus on the indisputable information needed to relay events. There should be reliable statistics. This includes the people involved, the places where it happened, and any additional important details and evidence.

Opinion: Opinion can be a specific point of view. Because every people have own opinion. An important part of the news involves an individual's interpretation of the meaning or impact of an event or facts.

Many journalists add opinion between facts. Because it can help the reader or viewer better understand the meaning of the facts. Though analysis may include quotes from people with different points of view, its purpose should be to explain, not to convince. Journalists have an obligation to present the facts and, while they can offer various theories as to the cause, they shouldn't assume a cause until it's confirmed. One way to recognize them is to look closely at whether the report is using the information to encourage the audience to purchase a particular product or support a candidate or cause. Sometimes they are labeled as "sponsored stories," but sometimes it's totally up to the reader to figure out that they're ads, not editorial content.

As I mentioned Media literacy and fact checking so important. It's not foremost for journalist and also people around us. Because nearly 40% of information on social media is fake or misinformation.

